

Effects of Medetomidine-Thiopentone Anaesthesia on Anaesthetic Indices and Vital Parameters in Donkeys (*Equus asinus*) in Maiduguri, Nigeria

Yusuf, Z. B.,^{1*} Zaifada, A. U^{2.}, Laku, D^{1.}, Stephen, J^{3.}, Umar, M. A^{1.}, and Mohammed, A^{1.}

¹Department of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

²Veterinary Teaching Hospital, University of Abuja Nigeria.

³Department of Veterinary, Theriogenology and Production, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author E-mail: zainabyusuf2012@gmail.com

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An experiment was conducted to investigate the effects of medetomidine and thiopentone intravenous (IV) anaesthesia on the anaesthetic indices and Vital parameters of healthy donkeys with mean body weights of 159 ± 16.63 Kg, and age 3.45 ± 0.50 years. Medetomidine was administered at a recommended dose of $5 \mu\text{g} / \text{Kg}$ while 10 % thiopentone was administered at 7 mg/Kg body. Anaesthetic indices and vital parameters were monitored and recorded. Temperature, heart rate and respiratory rates were measured before and during anaesthesia. The (mean \pm SD) onset of anaesthesia was 21.60 ± 9.48 sec; duration of anaesthesia (mean \pm SD) was 42.20 ± 5.12 min; time to standing (mean \pm SD) was 27.20 ± 8.79 min and recovery score, for 4 donkeys was good and for 1 donkey was satisfactory. The temperature, heart rate and

respiratory rate did not significantly differed ($p > 0.05$) from baseline data. The recovery from anaesthesia in all donkeys was uneventful. The quality of surgical anaesthesia produced coupled with minimal cardiopulmonary effects with uneventful recovery suggests that Medetomidine-Thiopentone total intravenous anaesthesia is a considerable promising injectable technique that can be used to produce extended anaesthesia under field conditions.

Keywords: Medetomidine, thiopentone, anaesthetic indices, vital parameters, Donkeys (*Equus asinus*)

INTRODUCTION

Alpha 2 receptor agonists have gained worldwide recognition in veterinary medicine due to their sedative, analgesic and muscle relaxation properties in large and small animals (Luna et al. 2000). Medetomidine is the newest alpha-2-agonist and has greater potency and economic efficacy than other alpha-2-agonists (Miksa et al., 2005; Umar et al., 2006). Medetomidine is an effective sedative in small animal (Sinclair, 2003) and

horses, (Umar et al., 2006; Yamashita et al., 2007). Alpha-2- adrenergic agonists related to: xylazine, detomidine, and romifidine. The α -2 agonists are widely used in equine practice for their sedative and analgesic effects (Valverde, 2010).

Thiopental is a barbiturate anaesthetic with an ultrashort action time due to its rapid redistribution into well perfused tissues and body fats (Tsai et al., 2007).

Thiopental produces a dose-dependent sedation, general anaesthesia, cortical depression and finally death by enhancing the action of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) at GABA receptor sites (Muir, 2009). Barbiturates have a long history of usage in induction and maintenance of short-term anaesthesia (Tsai et al., 2007), but have been mostly replaced by other drugs with a wider margin of safety. Abass et al. (1994) reported that, thiopental anaesthesia is characterized by a rapid onset and short duration of action, usually lasting (5 – 15 min), and thiopentone is therefore an ideal drug to rapidly increase the depth of anaesthesia, especially in cases of sudden movement during surgery in equids. The use of medetomidine-thiopentone combination anaesthesia in donkeys is poorly documented and has not been evaluated in the study area. This study therefore was conducted to determine the effects of medetomidine and thiopentone anaesthesia on the anaesthetic indices and vital parameters of healthy donkeys (*Equus asinus*) in Maiduguri, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals

Five apparently healthy donkeys of both sexes (3 Females and 2 Males) with a mean \pm SD body weight of 159 ± 16.63 kg, and aged 3.45 ± 0.50 years were used for the study. The donkeys were procured from the Maiduguri livestock market and kept in stables at Large animal clinic (LAC) housing unit of the University of Maiduguri veterinary teaching hospital. The donkeys were fed with wheat offals, groundnut husk, grasses, and water was provided *ad libitum*. They were dewormed with albendazole at 50 mg/kg and allowed to acclimatize for a period of one month during which they were screened for gastrointestinal parasites, haemoparasites and dewormed accordingly before the commencement of the experiment. Feed but not water was withheld from the donkeys for 12 h before anaesthesia.

Anaesthesia

Drugs used in the study were medetomidine (Domitor[®] Pfizer,UK) at 5 μ g/ Kg and 10% thiopental sodium (U Pental[®] Waren handels GmbH, Hamburg-Germany) at 7 mg/ Kg. Animals were pre-medicated with medetomidine using 18- gauge needle placed in the jugular vein. Five minutes later anaesthesia was induced with 10% thiopental sodium and as the animal became recumbent, a drip infusion line was instituted via the jugular vein and fluid therapy commenced with 5% dextrose saline (Juhel[®], Fabrique par Juhel Nig. Ltd., Awka, Anambra, Nigeria) as maintenance fluid set at 1 ml per 10 Kg body weight per minute. Attached to the drip infusion set was a three

way stopper for ease of blood collection. Thereafter blood was collected at 15 min interval during anaesthesia and at 1 h post anaesthesia.

Measurement of anaesthetic indices

The anaesthetic indices measured for each donkey were: Onset of anaesthesia, duration of anaesthesia, time to standing and recovery. Recovery was assessed according to Umar et al. (2006).

Measurement of vital parameters

Heart rate (beats/minute), respiratory rate (breaths/minute) and rectal temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) were measured.

Statistical analysis

Data generated were managed in Microsoft excel spread sheet (Microsoft corporation, USA). One way ANOVA was compared via GraphPad[®] Prism version 4.0. Descriptive statistics (mean \pm SD) were used to present results in tables and ($P < 0.05$) was considered significant.

RESULTS

The onset of anaesthesia was 21.60 ± 9.48 sec while duration of anaesthesia was 42.20 ± 5.12 min and time to standing was 27.20 ± 8.79 min. The value of heart rate at baseline was 43.80 ± 5.59 beats/ min and increased to 44.80 ± 9.63 at 10 min and dropped to 42.40 ± 8.56 at 20 min. It maintained almost the baseline value of 43.00 ± 11.36 at 30 min and dropped to 40.00 ± 4.76 at 40 min. However, all the values did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). The respiratory rate at baseline was 19.80 ± 5.36 breaths/min, it decreased at 20 min, but increased from 30 min up to 40 min. However, there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The temperature at baseline was $36.82 \pm 0.55^{\circ}$ C. It did not significantly differ ($P > 0.05$) all through the study (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the use of medetomidine (an alpha-2 adrenoceptor) agonist as sedatives and thiopentone (a barbiturate) as the anaesthetic induction agent. The anaesthetic indices of Onset of anaesthesia, duration of anaesthesia, time to standing and recovery score was recorded as well as vital parameters of heart rate, respiratory rate and temperature. The onset of anaesthesia was 21.60 ± 9.48 sec, while duration of anaesthesia was

Table 1. Vital parameter of donkeys (*Equus asinus*) given medetomidine (5 µg/kg) and thiopentone (7 mg/kg) anaesthesia on mean ± SD heart rate, respiratory rate and temperature in donkeys Maiduguri, Nigeria.

Time interval (minutes)	Heart rate (beats/minute)	Respiratory rate (breaths/minute)	Temperature (°C)
Baseline	43.80 ± 5.59 ^a	19.80 ± 5.36 ^c	36.82 ± 0.55 ^b
10	44.80 ± 9.63 ^a	18.20 ± 2.39 ^c	36.46 ± 0.66 ^b
20	42.40 ± 8.56 ^a	19.40 ± 3.29 ^c	36.26 ± 0.88 ^b
30	43.00 ± 11.36 ^a	21.80 ± 2.86 ^c	36.22 ± 0.92 ^b
40	40.00 ± 4.76 ^a	22.20 ± 3.11 ^c	36.28 ± 0.84 ^b

Values with same superscripts within a column are not significantly different (P>0.05).

42.20 ± 5.12 min. In a similar study by Rueangareerat et al. (2013), showed that the combination of thiopentone with xylazine and thiopentone with detomidine produced excellent induction but the onset of anaesthesia were 46.1±8.7 and 76.3±18.4 sec, for the xylazine and detomidine pre-medicated mules respectively. This is probably due to the difference in dose of thiopentone used 6 mg/kg compared to 7 mg/kg used in this study. Muir, (2009) reported that thiopental produces dose-dependent sedation in equine. The time to standing was 27.20 ± 8.79 min. This may be related with the dose of thiopentone used. It has been reported that higher and or repeated doses of thiopentone is associated with delayed recoveries; this is because recovery from thiobarbiturate anaesthesia occurs by redistribution from brain to muscle and fat with concomitant elimination of the drug from the body by liver metabolism (Sams et al.,1985; Jackson et al., 2004). Four donkeys had a good recovery and in one donkey it was satisfactory. The recovery from anaesthesia was uneventful. Rueangareerat et al. (2013) reported uneventful recoveries in mules following alpha-2-agonist-thiopentone combination anaesthesia. The heart rate did not vary significantly. Rueangareerat et al. (2013) who used an alpha-2-adrenoceptor; detomidine combined with thiopentone in mules had a similar finding. However, Mama et al. (2009) who used detomidine in horses recorded low heart rate compared to this study. The respiratory rates did not vary significantly. Rueangareerat et al. (2013) who used an alpha-2-adrenoceptor agonist detomidine combined with thiopentone in mules did not find any significant variation. The rectal temperature following anaesthesia tends to decrease with time. Although, the variation was not significantly different. However, decreased rectal temperatures were reported in goats and dogs by Umar and Irefin, (2013); and Akbar et al. (2014).

Conclusion

The study showed that medetomidine-thiopentone total intravenous anaesthesia have considerable promise as an injectable technique that can be used to produce extended intravenous anaesthesia under field conditions.

Authors` Declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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